

The Oxidation of Triethylene Tetrasulphide by means of Potassium Permanganate.

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Part I.

Oxidation with Alkaline Potassium Permanganate.

The oxidation of triethylene tetrasulphide with nitric acid has been shown to result in the break-up of the molecule with the formation of the corresponding disulphonic acid. Each of the sulphur atoms situated between a pair of carbon atoms is converted into a sulphone group while fission takes place between the two contiguous sulphur atoms with the formation of the sulphonic acid (J. C. S. Trans., 1923, 123, 2176) It seemed desirable to study the action of a less drastic oxidising agent like potassium permanganate which might be expected to yield the corresponding tetrasulphone. This expectation has been realised as will be shown below under Part II. When, however, the tetrasulphide is treated with alkaline potassium permanganate, instead of a tetrasulphone being formed, it breaks up according to the following scheme :

EXPERIMENTAL.

The tetrasulphide was suspended in water and treated with about 10 c. c. of a 3% solution of potassium permanganate and a little caustic potash solution. The

addition of the permanganate was repeated till there was a distinct excess of it. The temperature was all along kept at about 30°. The reaction was completed by finally heating on the water-bath. The mixture was cooled and the precipitated manganese peroxide brought into solution by passing sulphur dioxide. The solution was concentrated and the potassium and manganese sulphates which crystallised out were filtered off. Alcohol was next added to the concentrated liquid and the precipitate rejected. The alcohol was driven off, the residue dissolved in water and treated with barium carbonate. The precipitate was filtered off and the solution on evaporation gave crystals of the barium salt of ethylene disulphonic acid. The salt was air-dried and was found to be semi-hydrated. (Found: Ba=40.97; S=20.75.* $C_2H_4S_2O_6Ba$, $\frac{1}{3}H_2O$ requires Ba=41.02; S=19.16 per cent.).

Part II.

Oxidation with acid Potassium Permanganate.

On oxidation of the triethylene tetrasulphide with potassium permanganate in dilute sulphuric acid solution, a very interesting result is obtained. The expected sulphone formed during the reaction combines with the manganous sulphate produced and a stable double compound of the formula $[(C_2H_4)_3S_4O_8], MnSO_4, 6H_2O$ is invariably obtained. It has been found to be very sparingly soluble in the cold but dissolves readily in boiling water from which it crystallises out in the pure state. By adding

* The sulphonate was converted into sulphate by fusion with a mixture of KNO_3 and Na_2CO_3 . The 'melt' was repeatedly evaporated with conc. HCl to convert the excess of the nitrate as far as possible into the chloride. When the solution is treated with $BaCl_2$, a portion of the unconverted nitrate is almost invariably carried down with the $BaSO_4$; hence the p. c. of sulphur generally comes out a little too high.

barium chloride to this boiling solution, the corresponding compound with barium sulphate is at once thrown down. By a similar treatment compounds with the sulphates of calcium and strontium as also of potassium and lead have been obtained. With silver nitrate a double compound of silver sulphate is formed. Corresponding double compounds with the sulphates of nickel, cobalt, and copper have also been obtained by the addition of the respective chlorides. Peculiar interest attaches to some of these compounds, notably the combination of the sulphone with barium sulphate, as on account of its extreme insolubility all attempts to combine it with other compounds have hitherto been unsuccessful. But by following this indirect method, however, an additive compound with barium sulphate has been obtained. The sodium compound could not be isolated in a pure condition by a method analogous to that for the preparation of the potassium compound, a special procedure was therefore adopted.

In all these compounds the proportion of the respective metallic sulphate to the sulphone holds simple integral relationship. In the case of the barium compound alone the components are in the simple ratio of 1 : 1 ; whereas they are in the ratio of 2 : 3 in the manganese, copper, cobalt and nickel compounds. The ratio is as 4 : 5 in the potassium, calcium, strontium, silver and lead double compounds. The sodium compound alone gives a ratio of 4 : 1 between sodium sulphate and the sulphone.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The Oxidation of Triethylene Tetrasulphide with Acid Potassium Permanganate.—The tetrasulphide was treated with a mixture of a concentrated solution of potassium

permanganate and dilute sulphuric acid in small quantities at a time and heated on the water-bath. This process was continued till there remained a distinct excess of the permanganate. The oxidation was complete in the course of about 4 to 6 hours. The excess of permanganate was removed by passing a current of sulphur dioxide through the mixture. The solution became hot, leaving a residue of the unacted tetrasulphide, the latter was filtered off and the filtrate concentrated on the water-bath to nearly half its volume. On cooling, a colourless compound crystallised out. This was filtered, washed with cold water, and dried. (Found: Mn=7.38; S=28.86. $1\frac{1}{2}[(C_2H_4)_3S_4O_8]$, $MnSO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$ requires Mn=7.15; S=29.13 per cent.).

Calcium Compound.—The manganese compound was dissolved in boiling water and a concentrated solution of calcium chloride added to it. A white crystalline calcium compound was at once precipitated, which was filtered and dried. (Found: Ca=7.09; C=16.81. $1\frac{1}{2}[(C_2H_4)_3S_4O_8]$, $CaSO_4$ requires Ca=7.13; C=16.04 per cent.).

Strontium Compound.—This compound was prepared by a process similar to that used for the preparation of the calcium compound. (Found: Sr=14.68; C=14.66. $1\frac{1}{2}[(C_2H_4)_3S_4O_8]$, $SrSO_4$ requires Sr=14.38; C=14.80 per cent.).

Barium Compound.—This compound was also prepared like the calcium compound. (Found: Ba=23.24; S=26.25. $[(C_2H_4)_3S_4O_8]$, $BaSO_4 \cdot H_2O$ requires Ba=23.18; S=27.07 per cent.).

Lead Compound.—Lead chloride was dissolved in hot water and added to a solution of the manganese compound in boiling water. The precipitate was filtered, washed with hot water and dried. (Found: Pb=28.35. $1\frac{1}{2}[(C_2H_4)_3S_4O_8]$, $PbSO_4$ requires Pb=28.44 per cent.).

Silver Compound.—On adding a very concentrated solution of silver nitrate to a boiling solution of the manganese compound a white precipitate was at once thrown down. (Found: $\text{Ag}=29\cdot68$. $1\frac{1}{4}[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_3\text{S}_4\text{O}_8]$, Ag_2SO_4 requires $\text{Ag}=29\cdot31$ per cent.).

Copper, Cobalt and Nickel Compounds.—These products were obtained by adding a concentrated solution of the respective chlorides to a concentrated solution of the manganese double compound in hot water. The mixture on concentration and cooling gave crystals which were filtered, washed with a little cold water and dried. These compounds are fairly soluble in hot water. The copper compound is slightly bluish in colour. (Found: $\text{Cu}=9\cdot06$; $\text{S}=29\cdot55$. $1\frac{1}{2}[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_3\text{S}_4\text{O}_8]$, CuSO_4 , $4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires $\text{Cu}=8\cdot50$; $\text{S}=30\cdot23$ per cent.). The nickel compound is slightly greenish in colour. (Found: $\text{Ni}=8\cdot55$; $\text{S}=30\cdot03$. $1\frac{1}{2}[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_3\text{S}_4\text{O}_8]$, NiSO_4 , $4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires $\text{Ni}=7\cdot97$; $\text{S}=30\cdot40$ per cent.). The cobalt compound has a slight pink tint. (Found: $\text{Co}=8\cdot2$; $\text{S}=29\cdot28$. $1\frac{1}{2}[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_3\text{S}_4\text{O}_8]$, CoSO_4 , $4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires $\text{Co}=8\cdot00$; $\text{S}=30\cdot39$ per cent.).

The retention of the characteristic colours of the different metallic double compounds proves that the copper, nickel or cobalt atom does not form a component part of a complex.

Potassium Compound.—This compound was obtained as before by adding a concentrated solution of potassium chloride. There was no precipitate while the solution was hot, but on cooling a crystalline compound separated out. (Found: $\text{K}=12\cdot79$. $1\frac{1}{4}[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_3\text{S}_4\text{O}_8]$, K_2SO_4 requires $\text{K}=13\cdot02$ per cent.).

The Sodium Compound.—An aqueous solution of sodium carbonate was gradually added to a solution of the manganese compound till manganous carbonate was completely precipitated. This was filtered off and the

filtrate concentrated to a small bulk. On adding alcohol to this concentrated solution a syrup was obtained, which crystallised on keeping in a vacuum desiccator. The crystals were dissolved in water and reprecipitated with alcohol. (Found: Na=18.26; S=25.87. $\frac{1}{4}[(C_2H_5)_2S_2O_6]$, Na_2SO_4 , H_2O requires Na=18.77; S=26.12 per cent.).

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